

THE STATE OF THE WORLD TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS INFRASTRUCTURE AND TRANSPORT AND LOGISTIC SERVICES MARKET

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ANNOTATION

The research provides an overview of the state of the world transport and logistics infrastructure and transport and logistic services market. Globalisation of international economic relations imposes new requirements on the efficiency of transport and logistics infrastructure. The author studies the current state of the objects of world transport and logistics infrastructure, defines their essence and elaborates on their structure. The paper examines main trends in transport and logistics infrastructure development in recent years, paying special attention to the infrastructure objects of the rail transport, container transport as well as to port development. The author scrutinises the state and structure of the global transport and logistic services market, gives its geographical and product structure, and discovers the reasons behind the changes in the market structure.

Keywords: Transportation system, transport and logistics infrastructure; transport and logistic services; market; trend; global economy.

Introduction: World transport and logistics infrastructure and transport and logistic services market are developing in conditions of international integration processes. The impact of these processes on freight traffic is linked with countries' aspirations for more complete integration and manifests itself in creation of unified transport and logistic systems.

Multiple economic relations between countries kindle their mutual interest in building efficient integrated transport and logistics infrastructure with elements standardized to a maximum. Such kind of transport and logistics infrastructure should satisfy the requirements of high capacity and acceptable level of organisation and maintenance of the functioning of supply channels.

The goal of this paper is to assess the current state of the objects of the world transport and logistics infrastructure and analyse the transport and logistic services market. To achieve this goal the author is going to fulfil the following three tasks: first, to study main factors in transformation of the world transport and logistics infrastructure; second, to examine the condition of the objects of the world transport and logistics infrastructure; third, to justify the reasons behind the changes in the structure of the world transport and logistic services market.

Essence of the objects of transport and logistics infrastructure:

We regard transport and logistics infrastructure as a set of objects of transport and logistics subsystem of the national economy united by common tasks, processes and functions and forming single transport and logistic infrastructural space.

State of the world transport and logistic services market:

The state of the objects of the world transport and logistics infrastructure directly and indirectly affects the development of the world transport and logistic services market. Speaking about the direct impact, it is manifested in creation of the new segments of entrepreneurial activities in the field of transport and logistics, whereas the indirect impact is seen in encouraging the development of diverse forms of entrepreneurship in different countries of the world.

Some key developments include:

Expansion and improvement of road networks: Many countries have invested in expanding and upgrading their road networks to accommodate increasing traffic volume and improve connectivity between regions. This includes the construction of new highways, bridges, and tunnels, as well as the implementation of smart technologies for traffic management.

Emphasis on sustainable transportation: There's been a growing focus on sustainable transportation solutions such as electric vehicles, public transportation systems, and cycling infrastructure. Governments and businesses are investing in eco-friendly modes of transport to reduce emissions and combat climate change.

Modernization of ports and airports: Ports and airports have undergone extensive modernization to handle larger cargo volumes and accommodate bigger vessels and aircraft. This includes the construction of new terminals, the adoption of advanced cargo handling technologies, and the implementation of efficient customs and security procedures.

Integration of digital technologies: The logistics industry has embraced digital technologies such as GPS tracking, RFID, and blockchain to enhance supply chain visibility, optimize route planning, and improve inventory management. These technologies have streamlined operations and improved the accuracy and speed of deliveries.

Expansion of intermodal transportation: Intermodal transportation, which involves the seamless movement of freight between different modes of transport, has seen significant growth. This integration of multiple modes, such as rail, road, air, and sea, has enhanced the efficiency and flexibility of global supply chains.

Development of logistics hubs and distribution centers: The establishment of logistics hubs and distribution centers in strategic locations has improved warehousing, inventory management, and last-mile delivery capabilities. These hubs serve as key nodes in supply chains, facilitating the smooth flow of goods and reducing transportation costs.

Analysis and results:

In recent years, there has been significant development in transport and logistics infrastructure, driven by advancements in technology, urbanization, globalization, and the increasing demand for efficient supply chains.

Conclusions and offers:

Overall, the development of transport and logistics infrastructure in recent years has focused on enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and connectivity to meet the evolving needs of the global economy. Continued investment in infrastructure and ongoing technological advancements will further shape the future of transportation and logistics.

Overall, the world transport and logistics services market is a dynamic and evolving sector that plays a critical role in facilitating global trade and commerce. As the industry continues to adapt to changing market dynamics and technological advancements, it is expected to remain a key driver of economic growth and development.

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